

CORRECT ORGANIZATION OF INDEPENDENT EDUCATION - GUARANTEE OF QUALITY STAFF TRAINING

¹Nishonov Mirkozimjon, ²Khalikova Nozima Rahmonjonovna

¹Professor of the Department of Chemistry of Fergana State University, Candidate of Technical Sciences

²Teacher of organic chemistry department of Namangan State University

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Abstract. *This article highlights the unique aspects of organizing and conducting independent education in chemistry in the credit module system. The author's definitions of the concepts of independent education, independent work, imparting knowledge, and obtaining knowledge are given.*

Keywords: *credit module, independent education, independent work, education, quality education.*

Today, the most important of the reforms in the field of education in the Republic of Uzbekistan is the transition to the credit-module system of education in educational institutions.

For this, the regulatory and legal basis for the proper organization of the independent education process in our country has been fully created.

As evidence of our opinion, according to the "Concept for the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" established by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 8, 2019, 85 percent of the higher education institutions in the country will gradually introduce a credit module until 2030. we can show that it is planned to move to the system.

In addition, the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" and "On the National Program of Personnel Training", Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 "Uzbekistan Decree on the Action Strategy for Further Development of the Republic, PQ-2909 of April 20, 2017 "On Measures for the Further Development of the Higher Education System" and PQ of June 5, 2018 - Resolution No. 3775 "On additional measures to improve the quality of education in higher education institutions and ensure their active participation in comprehensive reforms implemented in the country", Higher and Order No. 233 of the Ministry of Special Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan dated March 27, 2020 "On the introduction of distance education in higher education institutions" lays the groundwork for improving the education system in our country.

The main goal of transitioning to the credit-module system is to train highly qualified personnel useful for society and competitive in the ever-growing labor market. The most important priorities for achieving this goal are the continuity and integrity of professional education, bringing the quality of education up to the level of world standards.

Today, a strong flow of information and new technologies is increasing. Due to scientific and technical progress, the amount of knowledge that humanity needs to acquire is increasing day by day. For example, in the field of chemistry, an average of 100 new synthesized substances are recognized every day around the world. Understandably, if we multiply this number by 366, it is necessary to reduce new scientific information in one year, that is, mankind has accumulated one can perceive how much the scope of chemical knowledge needs to go. At the same time, such a

sharp growth leads to the "obsolescence" of the previously acquired knowledge of specialists. According to the analysis of experts, 15-20% of knowledge is obsolete every year[1].

This situation promotes the idea of bringing the education system in line with the times, introducing continuous education that covers the whole life of a person based on the needs of the market economy. It is no exaggeration to say that the new, credit-module system of education, which is currently being implemented, includes the saying "Seek knowledge from the cradle to the grave", which has been promoted in our country for a long time. In the credit-module system, it is assumed that each of the students will receive education based on their abilities and interests and have equal opportunities with everyone.

The correct organization of students' independent learning process in the credit-module system is one of the most important problems of modern educational pedagogy. After all, as the saying goes in our people, it is better to teach your child to fish than to let him catch fish every day [2].

Today's educational tradition requires not just teaching the student, but researching all the pedagogical and psychological conditions necessary for the student to study. That is, it is necessary to replace the traditional "teaching" process in modern education with a new "learning". In this case, the student should not be a passive consumer of the taught knowledge, but should become an active creator of knowledge who has his own opinion on any issue related to science based on the acquired knowledge, can analyze the problem with understanding, approach the problem critically and find its solutions.

In fact, the cortex of the hemispheres of the human brain is structured in such a way that it has the ability to quickly forget or not accept unnecessary information. Therefore, it is urgent to organize the educational process within the specialization of students based on their own initiative, based on their interests and abilities.

Therefore, independent education means that students can acquire independent knowledge, freely analyze the topic, have their own opinion on the relevant issue, conduct scientific research, think freely, develop conclusions and proposals on problematic issues, and apply them to practice. serves for the formation of necessary knowledge and skills.

The student's independent work is an integral part of the educational work specified in the curriculum for mastering a particular subject. The student's independent work is a systematic activity aimed at mastering a certain part of the knowledge, skills and qualifications specified in the curriculum and the science program from a specific subject, based on the advice and recommendations of the subject teacher, in the classroom and outside the classroom.

Although the term "independent education" is widely used in practice, different researchers give different definitions to this concept, and there is still no single definition of this concept in scientific pedagogical literature. But this concept is actually more comprehensive than the concept of independent work. In our opinion, independent education is a systematic activity of a student aimed at acquiring knowledge independently without the direct support of a professor-teacher within a specific subject. It requires the student to concentrate both mental and practical activities. It leads to the development of psychological characteristics of the student, such as self-management, self-activation, self-organization, self-control. In the end, this serves to form the deep knowledge, knowledge and skills necessary for the student in his specialty.

Its result shows not only the student's level of knowledge, but also his skill and talent and serves to make him a competitive staff.

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